

SURVIVAL ANALYSIS OF A NEW GENERALIZATION OF EXPONENTIAL-EXPONENTIAL DISTRIBUTION AND ITS APPLICATIONS TO CANCER DATA

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ABSTRACT:

In statistics literature there are so many distributions which need generalisation or extension to make them more flexible and to aid their application in various fields like medicine, ecology and reliability and so on. The generalisation and extension are done with the help of families of distributions. This article deals with a new generalization of exponential-exponential distribution named as exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution with scale and shape parameters. Some statistical aspects of the novel distribution such as moments, moment generating and characteristic functions, mode and harmonic mean are derived. Reliability terms such as survival function, hazard function and reverse hazard functions are discussed. The plot of the pdf, cdf and reliability functions also included. We derive Bonferroni and Lorenz curve and density of order statistics. Maximum likelihood method is employed for estimating the parameters of the distribution. The superiority (with the help of likelihood values, AIC, BIC, AICC and HQIC) of the new model with some existing distribution is illustrated through a two cancer data sets. The results showed that the new model is better fit.

Keywords: exponential-exponential distribution, hazard function, exponentiated family of distribution, maximum likelihood estimation, order statistics, entropy measures.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of the exponentiated distribution was presented by Gupta et al. [3], who introduced a novel family of distributions called the exponentiated exponential distribution. This distribution family includes two parameters (scale and shape), similar to those of the Gamma and Weibull distributions. In their work, Gupta and Kundu [4] examined various properties of the distribution and noted that most of its features are very similar to those of the Gamma and Weibull families. Therefore, these distributions can be replaced by this novel

distribution. The two most widely used distributions for analysing lifetime data are the two-parameter Gamma and Weibull distributions. However, the inability to express the distribution function or survival function in closed form is a significant drawback of the Gamma distribution, as it is expressed in terms of an incomplete gamma function and must be obtained through numerical integration. In contrast, the Weibull distribution has closed-form expressions for the hazard, survival, and distribution functions. Swedish physicist Weibull [19] first proposed the Weibull distribution, which he used to illustrate the distribution of a material's breaking strength. The Weibull distribution has gained popularity recently for analysing lifespan data, mostly because it is significantly simpler to handle, at least numerically, than the Gamma distribution when censoring is present. Depending on the shape parameter, its failure rate can increase or decrease. The Weibull distribution in various ways used in [12] and [7].

Exponentiated distributions and their mathematical characteristics are currently being extensively researched for empirical data sets in applied science. The features and applications of the Exponentiated Ishita distribution and Exponentiated Mukherjee-Islam distributions were covered by in [13] and [14]. As an extension of the Weibull distribution, the Exponentiated Weibull family was examined by [11]. The Exponentiated Power Lindley distribution was developed and studied in [2], while the exponentiated generalised Lindley distribution was examined by [16]. The properties and uses of the Exponentiated Lomax Geometric distribution were covered by [6]. The properties and applications of the Exponentiated Pranav distribution were discussed in [18], and the features and applications of the Exponentiated Rama distribution were covered by [10]. The Exponentiated Garima distribution, which exhibits greater flexibility than the traditional distribution and an application in engineering, was examined by [15].

In this paper, we examine and derive several features of a two-parameter exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution. The generalization of the exponential-exponential distribution was introduced by [20], who discussed its theory and statistical properties. We use the exponentiated family distribution technique to derive this novel distribution, which we term the exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution. This distribution has two parameters: a shape parameter and a scale parameter. It also exhibits an increasing or decreasing failure rate depending on the value of the shape parameter. The major aim of the study is to develop a new model of the two-parameter distribution, with the expectation that the new distribution will provide a better fit than some standard distributions. Many properties, such as moments, moment-generating and characteristic functions, order statistics, and reliability properties, are discussed. In Section 2, we propose a new generalization of the exponential-exponential distribution, namely the exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution (Exponentiated EED). Various reliability properties of the proposed distribution are studied in Section 3. Characterizations of the Exponentiated EE distribution are obtained in Section 4. In Section 5, various entropy measures, including Rényi, Shannon, and Tsallis entropies, are discussed. Bonferroni and Lorenz curves are discussed in Section 6. In Section 7, we include the first and n th order statistics. The estimation of parameters of the proposed distribution using the method of maximum likelihood and the Fisher information matrix is addressed in Section 8. In Section

9, we fit the model to real-life data to demonstrate the flexibility of the new distribution. Concluding remarks are presented in Section 10.

2. EXPONENTIATED EXPONENTIAL-EXPONENTIAL DISTRIBUTION

The probability density function (pdf) of the Exponential-Exponential (EE) distribution by Ayeni [20] is given as

$$f(x) = \lambda^2 e^{-\lambda^2 x}, x > 0, \lambda > 0 \quad (1)$$

and the cumulative distribution function (cdf) of the Exponential-Exponential distribution is given by

$$F(x) = 1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}, x > 0, \lambda > 0 \quad (2)$$

Let X be a random variable with probability density function (pdf) $f(x)$ and the cumulative distribution function (cdf) $F(x)$, $x \in R$. Consider a random variable Z with cdf given by

$$G_\alpha(z) = [F(z)]^\alpha, z \in R, \alpha > 0 \quad (3)$$

Then Z is said to be an exponentiated distribution. The pdf of Z is given by

$$g_\alpha(z) = \alpha [F(z)]^{\alpha-1} f(z), z \in R, \alpha > 0. \quad (4)$$

By substituting (2) in (3), we will obtain the cumulative distribution function (cdf) of the Exponentiated Exponential Exponential (Exponentiated EE) distribution.

$$F_\alpha(x) = [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^\alpha, x > 0, \lambda > 0, \alpha > 0 \quad (5)$$

and the probability density function of Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution can be obtained as

$$f_\alpha(x) = \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}, x > 0, \lambda > 0, \alpha > 0 \quad (6)$$

where λ and α are the scale and shape parameters.

Figure 1: The pdf plot of Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution for different values of the parameters.

Figure 2: The cdf plot of Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution for different values of the parameters.

3. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

In this section we discuss about the survival function, hazard function, reverse hazard function and Mills Ratio of the Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution.

3.1. Survival Function:

The survival function of the Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution is given by

$$S(x; \lambda) = 1 - F(x; \lambda)$$

$$S(x; \lambda) = 1 - [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^\alpha \tag{7}$$

Figure 3: The survival function of Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution for different values of the parameters.

3.2. Hazard Function:

The hazard function or failure rate of the proposed distribution is given by

$$h(x) = \frac{f(x;\lambda)}{S(x;\lambda)}$$

$$h(x) = \frac{\alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}}{1 - [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^\alpha} \tag{8}$$

3.3. Reverse Hazard Function:

The reverse hazard function of the area biased exponential-exponential distribution is given by

$$h_r(x) = \frac{f(x; \theta)}{F(x; \theta)}$$

$$h_r(x) = \frac{\alpha \lambda^2 e^{-\lambda^2 x}}{1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}} \tag{9}$$

3.4. Mills Ratio:

The Mills Ratio of area biased exponential-exponential distribution is

$$\text{Mills Ratio} = \frac{1}{h_r(x)} = \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}}{\alpha \lambda^2 e^{-\lambda^2 x}} \tag{10}$$

4. STATISTICAL PROPERTIES

In this section we define and discuss the various statistical properties of Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution.

4.1. Moments and Related Measures:

Suppose X is a random variable following Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution with parameters λ and α , then the r^{th} order moment $E(X^r)$ for a given probability distribution is given by

$$E(X^r) = \mu'_r = \int_0^{\infty} x^r f(x; \lambda) dx$$

$$E(X^r) = \int_0^{\infty} x^r \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} dx$$

Substituting $u = 1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}$

$$E(X^r) = \alpha \int_0^1 \left[-\frac{1}{\lambda^2} \ln(1-u) \right]^r u^{\alpha-1} du$$

$$E(X^r) = \frac{\alpha}{\lambda^{2r}} \int_0^1 [-\ln(1-u)]^r u^{\alpha-1} du$$

$$E(X^r) = \frac{\alpha \Gamma(\alpha) \Gamma(r+1)^2}{\lambda^{2r} \Gamma(\alpha+r+1)} \quad (11)$$

The mean and variance can be obtained by substituting $r=1, 2, 3$ and 4

$$E(X) = \mu'_1 = \frac{1}{\lambda^2(\alpha+1)}$$

$$E(X^2) = \mu'_2 = \frac{4}{\lambda^4(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)}$$

$$E(X^3) = \mu'_3 = \frac{36}{\lambda^6(\alpha+3)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)}$$

$$E(X^4) = \mu'_4 = \frac{576}{\lambda^8(\alpha+4)(\alpha+3)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)}$$

$$\text{Variance} = \mu'_2 - (\mu'_1)^2 = \frac{3\alpha+2}{\lambda^4(\alpha+1)^2(\alpha+2)} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{SD} = \frac{\sqrt{3\alpha+2}}{\lambda^2(\alpha+1)\sqrt{\alpha+2}} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Skewness, } \gamma_1 = \frac{\mu_3}{\sigma^3} = \frac{\frac{36}{\lambda^6(\alpha+3)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)} - \frac{12}{\lambda^6(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{2}{\lambda^6(\alpha+1)^3}}{\left[\frac{\sqrt{(3\alpha+2)}}{\lambda^2(\alpha+1)\sqrt{(\alpha+2)}} \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Kurtosis, } \gamma_2 = \frac{\mu_4}{\sigma^4} = \frac{576}{\lambda^8(\alpha+4)(\alpha+3)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)} - \frac{144}{\lambda^8(\alpha+3)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{24}{\lambda^8(\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)^3} - \frac{3}{\lambda^8(\alpha+1)^4} \quad (15)$$

4.2. Moment Generating Function and Characteristic Function

In this sub section we derive the moment generating function and Characteristic function of Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution.

$$M_x(t) = E(e^{tx})$$

$$M_x(t) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{tx} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} dx$$

$$M_x(t) = \int_0^{\infty} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{(t-\lambda^2)x} dx$$

$$M_x(t) = \frac{\alpha \Gamma(\alpha) \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{t}{\lambda^2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 - \frac{t}{\lambda^2}\right)}, \text{ for } |t| < \lambda^2 \quad (16)$$

The Characteristic function of Exponentiated EE distribution is obtained as

$$\phi_x(t) = E(e^{itx}) = \frac{\alpha \Gamma(\alpha) \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{it}{\lambda^2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 - \frac{it}{\lambda^2}\right)} \quad (17)$$

4.3. Harmonic Mean:

The Harmonic mean of the proposed model can be obtained as

$$H.M = E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} f(x; \lambda) dx$$

$$H.M = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} dx$$

$$H.M = \alpha \lambda^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k(\alpha+k)} \quad (18)$$

4.4. Mode:

Mode is the value of x where $f(x)$ attains its maximum. The mode of the Exponentiated Exponential-Exponential distribution is given by, we have the pdf (6)

$$f_{\alpha}(x) = \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}$$

then the first derivative of $f_{\alpha}(x)$ is given by

$$f'_{\alpha}(x) = \alpha \lambda^4 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-2} [\alpha e^{-\lambda^2 x} - 1] e^{-\lambda^2 x}$$

$$f'_{\alpha}(x) = 0 \Rightarrow x = \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \ln(\alpha), \text{ for } \alpha > 1$$

and for $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, the mode is at $x=0$, since the density is monotonically decreasing.

$$\text{Mode} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \alpha \leq 1 \\ \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \ln(\alpha), & \text{if } \alpha > 1 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

5. ENTROPY MEASURES

The entropy of a random variable X is a measure of variation of the uncertainty. It plays important role in various fields, including probability and statistics, physics communication theory and economics by quantifying diversity and unpredictability. A system with higher entropy indicates greater uncertainty and more uniform outcomes. In this section we include the different entropy measures like Renyi entropy, Shannon entropy and Tsallis entropy.

5.1. Renyi Entropy:

The Renyi entropy is also important in quantum information, where it can be used as a measure of entanglement. For a given probability distribution, Renyi entropy is given by

$$R_{\mu}(f(x)) = \frac{1}{1-\mu} \log \int_0^{\infty} [f_{\alpha}(x)]^{\mu} dx, \text{ where } \mu > 0 \text{ and } \mu \neq 1$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} [f_{\alpha}(x)]^{\mu} dx = \int_0^{\infty} [\alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\mu} dx = \alpha^{\mu} \lambda^{2\mu-2} \frac{\Gamma(\mu) \Gamma(\mu(\alpha-1)+1)}{\Gamma(\mu\alpha+1)}$$

$$R_{\mu}(f(x)) = \frac{1}{1-\mu} \log \left[\alpha^{\mu} \lambda^{2\mu-2} \frac{\Gamma(\mu) \Gamma(\mu(\alpha-1)+1)}{\Gamma(\mu\alpha+1)} \right] \quad (20)$$

5.2. Shannon Entropy:

The Shannon entropy of the proposed distribution is given by

$$S_{\mu} = \int_0^{\infty} f(x) \log(f(x)) dx$$

$$S_{\mu} = \int_0^{\infty} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} \log(\alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}) dx$$

Substituting $u = 1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}$

$$S_{\mu} = \alpha \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} [\log(\alpha \lambda^2) + (\alpha - 1) \log u + \log(1 - u)] du$$

$$S_{\mu} = \log(\alpha \lambda^2) - \frac{\alpha-1}{\alpha} - [\varphi(1)] - \varphi(\alpha + 1) \quad (21)$$

5.3. Tsallis Entropy:

A generalization of Boltzmann-Gibbs (B-G) statistical mechanics initiated by Tsallis has focussed a great deal to attention. This generalization of B-G statistics was proposed firstly by introducing the mathematical expression of Tsallis entropy, for a continuous random variable is defined by [17] as follows.

$$T_{\mu} = \frac{1}{\mu - 1} \left[1 - \int_0^{\infty} f(x)^{\mu} dx \right]$$

$$T_{\mu} = \frac{1}{\mu-1} \left[1 - \int_0^{\infty} [\alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\mu} dx \right] \quad (22)$$

6. BONFERRONI AND LORENZ CURVES

The Bonferroni and Lorenz curve have applications not only in economics to study income and poverty, but also in other fields like reliability, demography, insurance and medical science. The Bonferroni curve of the Exponentiated EED is defined as:

$$B(p) = \frac{1}{p\mu} \int_0^q x f(x) dx = \frac{1}{p\mu} \left[\mu - \int_q^{\infty} x f(x) dx \right]$$

$$B(p) = \frac{1}{p\lambda^2(\alpha+1)} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda^2(\alpha+1)} - \int_q^{\infty} x \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} dx \right] \quad (23)$$

The Lorenz curve of the Exponentiated EED is defined as:

$$L(p) = \frac{1}{\mu} \int_0^q x f(x) dx = \frac{1}{\mu} \left[\mu - \int_q^{\infty} x f(x) dx \right]$$

$$L(p) = \frac{1}{\lambda^2(\alpha+1)} \left[\lambda^2(\alpha+1) - \int_q^{\infty} x \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} dx \right] \quad (24)$$

7. ORDER STATISTICS

Order statistics make their appearance in many statistical theory and practice. We know that if $X_{(1)}, X_{(2)}, \dots, X_{(n)}$ denotes the order statistics of a random sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n from a continuous population with cdf $F_x(x)$ and pdf $f_x(x)$, then the pdf of r^{th} order statistics $X_{(r)}$ is given by,

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \cdot f_x(x) \cdot [F_x(x)]^{r-1} [1 - F_x(x)]^{n-r}$$

Using the pdf and cdf in the above equation, we will obtain the probability density function of r^{th} order statistics of exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution as

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} \left[[1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^\alpha \right]^{r-1} [e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{n-r}$$

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} \left[[1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^\alpha \right]^{r-1} [e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{n-r}$$

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha r-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x(n-r+1)} \quad (25)$$

The probability density function of first order statistic $X_{(1)}$ of exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution can be obtained as

$$f_{x(1)}(x) = n \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-n\lambda^2 x} \quad (26)$$

Similarly, the probability density function of higher order statistic $X_{(n)}$ of exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution can be obtained as

$$f_{x(n)}(x) = n \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha n-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x} \quad (27)$$

8. PARAMETER ESTIMATION AND FISHER INFORMATION MATRIX

In this section we estimate the parameter of exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution using method of maximum likelihood. Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample of size n from the length biased exponential-exponential distribution, then the likelihood function is given by,

$$L(x, \lambda, \alpha) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(x, \lambda, \alpha)$$

$$L(x, \lambda, \alpha) = \prod_{i=1}^n \alpha \lambda^2 [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x}$$

$$L(x, \lambda, \alpha) = (\alpha \lambda^2)^n \prod_{i=1}^n [1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x_i}]^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda^2 x_i} \quad (28)$$

The log likelihood function is given by

$$\log L(x; \lambda, \alpha) = n \log \alpha + 2n \log \lambda + (\alpha - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x_i}) - \lambda^2 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

Differentiating the above equation partially w.r.to λ and α and equating to zero, we get the following system of normal equations.

$$\frac{n}{\hat{\alpha}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 - e^{-\hat{\lambda}^2 x_i}) = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{2n}{\hat{\lambda}} + 2 \hat{\lambda} (\hat{\alpha} - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i e^{-\hat{\lambda}^2 x_i}}{1 - e^{-\hat{\lambda}^2 x_i}} - 2 \hat{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 0 \quad (30)$$

These normal equations form a non-linear system in $\hat{\lambda}$ and $\hat{\alpha}$. Since there is no closed form solution, it may solve numerically by the help of R programming or wolfram Mathematica.

We have Fisher information matrix $I^{-1}(\alpha, \lambda)$ as

$$I(\alpha, \lambda) = -\frac{1}{n} E \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \lambda^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \lambda \partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha \partial \lambda} & \frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Where,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \lambda^2} = -\frac{2n}{\lambda^2} - 2 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + 2(\alpha - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i e^{-\lambda^2 x_i}}{1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x_i}}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha^2} = -\frac{n}{\lambda^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \lambda \partial \alpha} = \frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha \partial \lambda} = 2\lambda \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i e^{-\lambda^2 x_i}}{1 - e^{-\lambda^2 x_i}}$$

To find the asymptotic confidence interval for α and λ , we estimate $I(\alpha, \lambda)$. We can determine the results by $\sqrt{n} ((\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\lambda}) - (\alpha, \lambda)) \rightarrow N_2 [0, I^{-1}(\alpha, \lambda)]$.

9. DATA ANALYSIS

The real-life application of exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution is included in this section and show that the exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution can be a

better model than the exponential-exponential distribution, exponential distribution, Weibull and Gamma distributions. The data set is given below.

Data Set 1: This data represents the survival data times of 63 patients with breast cancer has suggested by Ramos et. al. [21] as shown below.

10.3, 11.0, 11.8, 12.2, 12.3, 13.5, 14.4, 14.8, 15.7, 16.3, 16.8, 16.5, 17.2, 17.3, 17.5, 17.9, 20.4, 21.0, 23.0, 23.4, 24.0, 24.0, 27.9, 28.2, 29.1, 30.0, 31.0, 31.0, 32.0, 35.0, 35.0, 37.0, 37.0, 38.0, 39.0, 41.0, 51.0, 54.0, 56.0, 57.0, 58.0, 59.0, 60.0, 60.0, 60.0, 90.0, 93.0, 96.0, 103.0, 104.0, 105.0, 109.0, 109.0, 111.0, 115.0, 117.0, 125.0, 126.0, 127.0, 129.0, 129.0, 139.0, 154.0.

Data Set 2: We consider a data set of 40 patients suffering from blood cancer (leukaemia) from one of Ministry of health hospitals in Saudi Arabia, Abouammahet al. [1]. The data set is given as follows:

0.315 0.496 0.616 1.145 1.208 1.263 1.414 2.025 2.036 2.162 2.211 2.37 2.532 2.693 2.805 2.91 2.912 3.192 3.263 3.348 3.348 3.427 3.499 3.534 3.767 3.751 3.858 3.986 4.049 4.244 4.323 4.381 4.392 4.397 4.647 4.753 4.929 4.973 5.074 5.381.

In order to compare the performance, exponentiated exponential- exponential distribution (Exponentiated EED) with exponential-exponential distribution (EED) and exponential distribution (ED), Weibull Distribution (WD) and Gamma Distribution (GD), we are using the Criterion values like AIC (Akaike information criterion), AICC (corrected Akaike information criterion), BIC (Bayesian information criterion) and HQIC (Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion). The better distribution corresponds to lesser AIC, AICC, BIC and HQIC values. The formulae for calculation of AIC, BIC, AICC and HQIC are;

$$AIC = 2k - 2 \log L, AICC = AIC + \frac{2k(k+1)}{n-k-1}, BIC = k \log n - 2 \log L \text{ and}$$

$$HQIC = 2k \log (\log(n)) - 2 \log L.$$

where n is the sample size, K is the number of parameters, and L denotes the likelihood function and C we take it as 2. Any probability model having smaller value of AIC, BIC and $-LogL$ being the best model to fit the data set.

Comparison and Performance of the fitted Distributions

Table 1: MLE's, AIC, BIC, AICC, HQIC and FIC for the bladder cancer data

Distributions	MLE	-Log L	AIC	BIC	AICC	HQIC
Exponentiated EED	$\hat{\alpha}=1.875$ $\hat{\lambda}= 0.1632$	-309.80	623.60	627.89	623.80	625.29

EED	$\hat{\lambda} = 0.1354$	-314.98	631.96	634.10	632.02	632.80
ED	$\hat{\lambda} = 0.01832$	-314.98	631.96	634.10	632.02	632.80
WD	$\hat{\alpha} = 1.358$ $\hat{\lambda} = 59.933$	-310.741	625.481	629.767	625.681	627.167
GD	$\hat{\alpha} = 1.753$ $\hat{\lambda} = 31.133$	-309.934	623.869	628.155	624.069	625.554

Table 2: MLE's, AIC, BIC, AICC, HQIC and FIC for the blood cancer data.

Distributions	MLE	-Log L	AIC	BIC	AICC	HQIC
Exponentiated EED	$\hat{\alpha} = 3.518$ $\hat{\lambda} = 0.7836$	-74.962	153.9249	157.3026	154.2492	155.1461
EED	$\hat{\lambda} = 0.5642$	-85.7781	173.556	175.2451	173.6615	174.1669
ED	$\hat{\lambda} = 0.3183$	-85.7781	173.5563	175.2451	173.6615	174.1669
WD	$\hat{\alpha} = 2.4992$ $\hat{\lambda} = 3.5182$	-89.55796	183.1159	186.4937	183.4402	184.3372
GD	$\hat{\alpha} = 3.465$ $\hat{\lambda} = 0.906$	-83.549	161.097	164.475	161.422	162.319

AIC, BIC, AICC, -Log L, and HQIC values are lower in the Exponentiated EED than in the EED, ED, WD and GD according to Table 1 and Table 2. Our conclusion is that the Exponentiated EED provides a better fit than other distribution.

Figure 4: Estimated PDF plot of Exponentiated EE distribution and other competitive models for the data sets 1 & 2.

Figure 5: Empirical CDF and Fitted CDFs for the data sets 1 & 2.

10. CONCLUSION

In this present article, we have proposed a new generalization of the exponential-exponential distribution called as Exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution with two parameters by exponentiated technique. The statistical and reliability properties have been obtained. Maximum likelihood estimation technique is used for estimating the parameters of the proposed distribution. The goodness of fit of the proposed distribution has been compared with two real life data sets. Finally, the results of two cancer data sets have been compared over one-parameter and two-parameter distributions and it has been found that the Exponentiated exponential-exponential distribution provides better fit than the comparing distributions.

Conflict of Interests

There is no conflict of interest declared by the author(s).

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